

ACUTE CORONARY SINDROM AND RAPID EARLY ACTION FOR CORONARY TREATMEN

Sharapova Nozima Erkinjonovna

Teacher of the Department Fundamental Medicine Disciplines Asia
International University

E-mail: sharapovanozimaerkinjonovna@oxu.uz

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Abstract: Lack of timely contact with the health care system leading to out-of-hospital death or delayed presentation remains a major obstacle to more effective management of patients with AMI.

Key words: reperfusion, arrhythmias, mortality, troponin, STEMI, NSTEMI-ACS.

Clinical trials of therapy for acute myocardial infarction (AMI) demonstrate the potential to limit infarct size and decrease mortality by coronary reperfusion and arrhythmia control. The effectiveness of these treatments is dependent on time and access to acute medical care. Coronary reperfusion requires early administration of thrombolytic agents or angioplasty. Defibrillation and other methods to control cardiac arrhythmias require trained personnel and equipment in an appropriate clinical setting. Although the need for timely receipt of these therapeutic strategies is well recognized, rapid access to emergency medical care remains a major problem. The majority of time lost is the period from the onset of symptoms to presentation in a medical facility, sometimes referred to as patient delay. Even when the decision is made to seek medical care, most patients in the United States avoid ambulance services, preferring self-transport. These delays, which average several hours, prevent the early application of life-saving procedures and contribute substantially to a diminished effectiveness of treatment.

Lack of timely contact with the health care system leading to out-of-hospital death or delayed presentation remains a major obstacle to more effective management of patients with AMI. The majority of CHD patients who die from cardiac arrest die outside the hospital without receiving medical attention. For those who experience AMI, delay in treatment is the major factor limiting the effectiveness of contemporary management approaches. Delay in seeking care is commonly divided into 3 major components: prehospital patient delay (time from symptom onset to seeking medical care); transportation delay; and delay in hospital evaluation and diagnosis prior to treatment.

Acute coronary syndrome (ACS) is associated with high mortality rates. Although the goal was to achieve a missed diagnosis rate of << 1%, the actual data showed a rate of >> 2%. Chest pain diagnosis has remained unchanged over the years and is based on medical interviews and electrocardiograms (ECG), with biomarkers playing complementary roles. We aimed to summarize the key points of medical interviews, ECG clinics, use of biomarkers, and clinical scores, identify problems, and provide directions for future research. Medical interviews should focus on the character and location of chest pain (is it accompanied by radiating pain?) and the duration, induction, and ameliorating factors. An ECG should be recorded within 10 minutes of the presentation. The serial performance of an ECG is recommended for emergency department (ED) evaluation of suspected ACS. Characteristic ECG traces, such as Wellens syndrome and De Winter T-waves, should be understood. Therefore, troponin levels

in all patients with suspected ischemic heart disease should be examined using a highly sensitive assay system. Depending on the ED facility, the patient should be risk stratified by serial measurements of cardiac troponin levels (re-testing at one hour would be preferred) to determine the appropriate time to perform an invasive strategy for a definitive diagnosis. The diagnostics should be based on Bayes' theorem; however, care should be taken to avoid the influence of heuristic bias.

In the last 10 years clinicians have been faced with the dilemma which platelet P2Y₁₂ receptor antagonist to choose for the treatment of patients with acute coronary syndrome (ACS). This is because two P2Y₁₂ receptor antagonists, prasugrel¹ and ticagrelor², had shown superior efficacy over their predecessor, clopidogrel, in large scale randomized clinical trials and received a class I recommendation in the guidelines.³ The decision making process was further complicated by the fact that, according to guidelines, the 2 new drugs were to be administered in 2 different ways in patients with non-ST-segment elevation ACS (NSTEMI-ACS). Available evidence supports routine initiation of ticagrelor as soon as the diagnosis of NSTEMI-ACS was established without waiting for the results of diagnostic angiography.^{2,3} The recommendation is different for prasugrel. In patients with NSTEMI-ACS, initiation of prasugrel was dependent on the findings of diagnostic angiography.^{1,3} The reason behind are the results of a specifically designed trial that showed that pretreatment with prasugrel was not only not beneficial but also harmful in patients with NSTEMI-ACS.⁴ The lack of head to head comparison trials of ticagrelor vs. prasugrel given over one year for the whole spectrum of ACS made difficult the decision of whether to embrace a ticagrelor-based strategy with routine pretreatment or a prasugrel-based strategy that requires waiting for the results of diagnostic angiography before starting prasugrel treatment in patients with NSTEMI-ACS. The Intracoronary Stenting and Antithrombotic Regimen: Rapid Early Action for Coronary Treatment (ISAR-REACT) 5 trial was an investigator-initiated, randomized, multicenter, open label trial that compared a ticagrelor- with a prasugrel-based strategy in 4,018 patients.^{5,6} The study hypothesis was that ticagrelor is superior to prasugrel. However, contrary to our expectation, the primary endpoint of death, myocardial infarction, or stroke at one year was observed significantly more frequently with the ticagrelor-based strategy (9.3% in the ticagrelor group 6.9% in the prasugrel group, hazard ratio, 1.36; 95% confidence interval [CI], 1.09 to 1.70; P = 0.006, Figure 1). The superiority of prasugrel was consistent across the ACS subsets irrespective of whether the patients presented with ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) or NSTEMI-ACS. Importantly, the increased efficacy of prasugrel (26% reduction in the risk of the primary endpoint) did not occur at the expense of an increased bleeding risk. Major bleeding (defined as Bleeding Academic Research Consortium (BARC) type 3-5) was observed in 5.4% of patients in the ticagrelor group and in 4.8% of patients in the prasugrel group (hazard ratio, 1.12; 95% CI, 0.83 to 1.51; P = 0.46; Figure 1).⁶ The ISAR-REACT 5 trial provides two main lessons: Firstly, prasugrel is a more effective antiplatelet drug than ticagrelor in ACS patients. The best clue to this is provided by the subset of STEMI patients in whom pretreatment was the starting strategy for both study drugs. Secondly, pretreatment with ticagrelor does not offer any advantage in patients with NSTEMI-ACS. Although there was no study arm without ticagrelor pretreatment in the ISAR-REACT 5 trial, taken together, our trial and the A Comparison of prasugrel at the time of percutaneous Coronary intervention Or as pre-treatment At the time of diagnosis in patients with non-ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (ACCOAST) trial offer evidence that pretreatment is

not needed in this subset of ACS patients. A few major characteristics of the ISAR-REACT 5 trial should be taken into consideration before extrapolating its results to the everyday practice. Notably, the study population in this trial is characterized by a very high proportion of patients treated with PCI and a very low proportion of patients treated with CABG or conservatively. Having said that, the results of the ISAR-REACT 5 trial are going to simplify the antiplatelet treatment algorithm of patients with ACS, making of prasugrel – in an individualized dose regimen – the mainstay of this treatment in all cases without specific contraindications to its use. While the diagnosis of STEMI is relatively straightforward and allows for starting prasugrel at the time of admission, in all patients with NSTEMI-ACS, initiation of prasugrel is dependent on the findings of diagnostic angiography.

Literatures:

1. Nozima, S. (2023). CLINICAL AND PATHOGENETIC ASPECTS OF THE COURSE AND TREATMENT OF HYPERTENSION. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE, 3(11), 25-29.
2. Erkinjonovna, S. N. (2024). THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FOOD AND BLOOD PRESSURE. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE, 4(4), 191-197.
3. Sharapova, N. (2023). ARTERIAL GIPERTENZIYA VA SEMIZLIK KASALLIKLARINING O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIK SABABLARI VA METABOLIK SINDROMLAR. Центральноеазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 2(11 Part 2), 174-179.
4. Шарাপова, Н. (2023). КЕКСА ВА ҚАРИ ЁШЛИ АЁЛЛАРДА БЕЛ АЙЛАНАСИНИНГ ЖИСМОНИЙ ФАОЛЛИК БИЛАН БОҒЛИҚЛИГИ ҚИЁСИЙ ТАҲЛИЛИ. Центральноеазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 2(12 Part 2), 127-133.
5. Erkinjonovna, S. N. (2023). DIABETES MELLITUS IN PREGNANT WOMEN. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 110-116.
6. Erkinjonovna, S. N. (2024). CHARACTERISTICS OF DENTAL PROSTHESES WEARING IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES ACCORDING TO KIDNEY IMPAIRMENT. PEDAGOG, 7(1), 84-88.
7. Erkinjonovna, S. N. (2024). THE BEST WAYS TO CONTROL HIGH BLOOD PRESSURE WITHOUT MEDICATION. Journal of new century innovations, 47(2), 175-183.
8. Narzulaeva Umida Rakhmatulloevna and Rakhmatova Fotima Ulugbekovna, "PATHOGENETIC MECHANISMS OF DISORDERS IN THE HEMOSTASIS SYSTEM OBSERVED IN PATIENTS INFECTED WITH COVID-19", IEJRD - International Multidisciplinary Journal, vol. 7, no. ICMEI, p. 3, Feb. 2023.
9. Narzulaeva, U. (2023). PATHOGENETIC SIGNIFICANCE OF HYPERLIPIDEMIA IN THE CLINICAL COURSE OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION. International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research, 3(11), 86-91.
10. Narzulaeva, U. (2023). PATHOGENETIC SIGNIFICANCE OF HYPERLIPIDEMIA IN THE CLINICAL COURSE OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION. International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research, 3(11), 86-91.
11. Нарзуллаева, У., Самиева, Г., & Пардаева, З. (2022). ПАТОФИЗИОЛОГИЯ РЕПЕРФУЗИОННОГО ПОВРЕЖДЕНИЯ МИОКАРДА. Журнал вестник врача, 1(2), 155–158. <https://doi.org/10.38095/2181-466X-2020942-154-157>

12. Самиева, Г., Нарзулаева, У., & Самиев, У. (2023). Течение артериальной гипертензии у жителей засушливого региона. Каталог монографий, 1(1), 1–108. извлечено от <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/monographs/article/view/27456>
13. Oripova, O. O., Samieva, G. U., Xamidova, F. M., & Narzulaeva, U. R. (2020). Sostoyanie plotnosti raspredeleniya limfoidnykh kletok slisistoy obolochki gortani va proyavleniya mestno immuna pri xroncheskom laringite (tahlil seksionnogo material). Akademiya, (4 (55)), 83-86.
14. Rakhmatulloevna, N. U., & Abdurasulovna, B. M. (2022). GEMOREOLOGIK BUZILISHLAR VA ERITROTSITLAR AGREGATSION XOSSALARI O'ZGARISHINING PATOGENETIK MEKANIZMLARI. JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE, 7(6).
15. Saloxiddinova, X. Y. (2024). Modern Views on the Effects of the Use of Cholecalciferol on the General Condition of the Bod. JOURNAL OF HEALTHCARE AND LIFE-SCIENCE RESEARCH, 3(5), 79-85.
16. Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). МОРФО-ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ И КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ СТРОЕНИЯ И РАЗВИТИЯ ЯИЧНИКОВ (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ). TADQIQOTLAR. UZ, 40(5), 188-198.
17. Халимова, Ю. С. (2024). Морфологические Особенности Поражения Печени У Пациентов С Синдромом Мэллори-Вейса. Journal of Science in Medicine and Life, 2(6), 166-172.
18. Xalimova, Y. S. (2024). Morphology of the Testes in the Detection of Infertility. Journal of Science in Medicine and Life, 2(6), 83-88.
19. Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). ОСОБЕННОСТИ СОЗРЕВАНИЕ И ФУНКЦИОНИРОВАНИЕ ЯИЧНИКОВ. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 55(2), 188-194.
20. Хафизова, М. Н., & Халимова, Ю. С. (2024). МОТИВАЦИОННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ ЛАТЫНИ И МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИИ. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 55(2), 165-171.
21. Хафизова, М. Н., & Халимова, Ю. С. (2024). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ЧАСТОТНЫХ ОТРЕЗКОВ В НАИМЕНОВАНИЯХ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННЫХ ПРЕПАРАТОВ В ФАРМАЦЕВТИКЕ. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 55(2), 172-178.
22. Saloxiddinova, X. Y., & Ne'matillaevna, X. M. (2024). FEATURES OF THE STRUCTURE OF THE REPRODUCTIVE ORGANS OF THE FEMALE BODY. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 55(2), 179-183.
23. Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ЛИЦ ЗЛОУПОТРЕБЛЯЮЩЕЕСЯ ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКИМИ НАПИТКАМИ. TADQIQOTLAR. UZ, 40(5), 199-207.
24. Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ВНУТРЕННИХ ОРГАНОВ У ЛИЦ, СТРАДАЮЩИХ АЛКОГОЛЬНОЙ ЗАВИСИМОСТЬЮ. TADQIQOTLAR. UZ, 40(5), 240-250.
25. Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). кафедра Клинических наук Азиатский международный университет Бухара, Узбекистан. Modern education and development, 10(1), 60-75.
26. Халимова, Ю. С., & Хафизова, М. Н. (2024). МОРФО-ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ И КЛИНИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ КОЖНЫХ ПОКРОВОВ. Modern education and development, 10(1), 76-90.

27. Nematilloevna, K. M., & Salokhiddinova, K. Y. (2024). IMPORTANT FEATURES IN THE FORMATION OF DEGREE OF COMPARISON OF ADJECTIVES IN LATIN. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 55(2), 150-157.
28. KHALIMOVA, Y. S. (2024). MORPHOFUNCTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF TESTICULAR AND OVARIAN TISSUES OF ANIMALS IN THE AGE ASPECT. *Valeology: International Journal of Medical Anthropology and Bioethics*, 2(9), 100-105.
29. Salokhiddinova, K. Y., Saifiloevich, S. B., Barnoevich, K. I., & Hikmatov, A. S. (2024). THE INCIDENCE OF AIDS, THE DEFINITION AND CAUSES OF THE DISEASE. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 55(2), 195-205.
30. Saidova, L. B., & Ergashev, G. T. (2022). Improvement of rehabilitation and rehabilitation criteria for patients with type 2 diabetes.
31. Эргашева, Г. Т. (2023). Изучение Клинических Особенности Больных Сахарным Диабетом 2 Типа Среднего И Пожилого Возраста. *Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science*, 4(6), 274-276.
32. Toxirovna, E. G. (2023). O'RTA VA KEKSA YOSHLI BEMORLARDA 2-TUR QANDLI DIABET KECISHINING KLINIKO-MORFOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 33(1), 164-166.
33. Ergasheva, G. T. (2022). QANDLI DIABET BILAN KASALLANGANLARDA REABILITATSIYA MEZONLARINI TAKOMILASHTIRISH. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(12), 335-337.
34. Ergasheva, G. (2024). METHODS TO PREVENT SIDE EFFECTS OF DIABETES MELLITUS IN SICK PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES. *Журнал академических исследований нового Узбекистана*, 1(2), 12-16.
35. ГТ, Э., & Саидова, Л. Б. (2022). СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ РЕАБИЛИТАЦИОННО-ВОССТАНОВИТЕЛЬНЫХ КРИТЕРИЕВ БОЛЬНЫХ С СД-2 ТИПА. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(12), 206-209.
36. Samixovna, M. X. (2024). OITS KASALLIGI, TA'RIFI VA KASALLIKNING KELIB CHIQISH SAVABLARI. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 55(2), 122-133.
37. Мухитдинова, Х. С. (2024). РАЗВИТИЕ ЯИЧНИКОВ, ИХ МОРФОЛОГИЯ И ОСОБЕННОСТИ ФУНКЦИОНИРОВАНИЕ. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 55(2), 134-141.
38. Мухитдинова, Х. С. (2024). СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ НА РАЗВИТИЕ БАКТЕРИАЛЬНОГО ВАГИНОЗА У ЖЕНЩИН ФЕРТИЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 55(2), 97-103.
39. Мухитдинова, Х. С. (2024). ЗАБОЛЕВАЕМОСТЬ СПИДОМ, МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ БОЛЕЗНИ. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 55(2), 104-112.
40. Samikhovna, M. K. (2024). Clinical and Morphological Aspects of the Functioning of the Lymphatic System. *International Journal of Alternative and Contemporary Therapy*, 2(9), 101-106.
41. Samikhovna, M. K. (2024). MODERN VIEWS ON ACROMEGALY AND IMMUNOMORPHOLOGY OF THIS DISEASE. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(10), 179-183.

42. Abdurashitovich, Z. F. (2024). Department of Syndesmology from the Science of Human Anatomy General Information About. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 3(3), 158-165.
43. Abdurashitovich, Z. F. (2024). THE COMPLEXITY OF THE FUSION OF THE BONES OF THE FOOT. *JOURNAL OF HEALTHCARE AND LIFE-SCIENCE RESEARCH*, 3(5), 223-230.
44. Abdurashitovich, Z. F. (2024). MUSHAKLAR TO'GRISIDA MA'LUMOT. MUSHAKLARNING TARAQQIYOTI. MUSHAKLARNING YORDAMCHI APPARATI. TADQIQOTLAR. UZ, 40(3), 94-100.
45. Abdurashitovich, Z. F. (2024). APPLICATION OF MYOCARDIAL CYTOPROTECTORS IN ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASES. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 39(5), 152-159.
46. Abdurashitovich, Z. F. (2024). SIGNIFICANCE OF BIOMARKERS IN METABOLIC SYNDROME. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(9), 409-413.
47. Qilichovna, A. M., & Nematilloevna, X. M. (2024). TIBBIYOT TILI HISOBLANMISH LOTIN TILINI SAMARALI O'RGANISH OMILLARI: Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari. Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotida tadqiqotlarni o'rni va rivojlanish omillari, 6(4), 197-206.
48. Tog'aydullayeva, D. D. (2024). Embrional Davrda Gemopoez Va Unda Jigar Va Taloqning Roli. *Journal of Science in Medicine and Life*, 2(6), 132-134.
49. Tog'aydullayeva, D. D. (2024). Occurrence of Combination Diseases in Ischemic Heart Disease and Metabolic Syndrome and their Diagnosis. *Journal of Science in Medicine and Life*, 2(6), 126-131.
50. TOG'AYDULLAYEVA, D. D. (2024). GLUCOSE TOLERANCE AND HYPERTENSION. *Valeology: International Journal of Medical Anthropology and Bioethics*, 2(09), 132-136.
51. Tog'aydullayeva, D. D. (2024). The Occurrence of Burning Diseases when Ischemic Heart Disease and Metabolic Syndrome Come Together. *AMALIY VA TIBBIYOT FANLARI ILMIY JURNALI*, 3(5), 432-437.

